

Kusniec's Theorem: Demonstrating Prime Numbers Between Squares and the Two Adjacent Oblong Numbers

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Abstract: This study aims to provide proof for an extension of Legendre's Conjecture by demonstrating the existence of at least one prime number between a perfect square and its successive oblong number, and vice versa. Specifically, we establish that for any integer $n \geq 1$, there is at least one prime p such that $n^2 - n < p < n^2$ and at least one distinct prime q such that $n^2 < q < n^2 + n$. Consequently, this implies the presence of at least two prime numbers between the squares of consecutive natural numbers and at least two prime numbers between consecutive oblong numbers. Our findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the distribution of prime numbers within these intervals and support the broader implications of Legendre's Conjecture in number theory.

Keywords: Legendre Conjecture, Fundamental Theorem of Arithmetic, Divisibility in Number Theory, Odd Divisors, Prime Number Distribution, Prime Numbers, Composite Numbers, Oblong Numbers, Square Numbers, Parabolic Sieve, Geometric Number Theory, Kusniec's Theorem.

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"To avoid growing cold, remind yourself that you can learn anything you want. But, to avoid becoming conceited, remind yourself that, no matter how much you know, there will always be more to learn." I often recall reading this phrase printed on the cover of my first school notebooks, between the years 1964 and 1968, a period when Rui Barbosa was declared the author.

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"Para não arrefeceres, lembra-te de que podes aprender qualquer coisa que queiras. Mas, para não ensoberbeceres, lembra-te de que, não importa quanto saibas, sempre haverá mais a aprender." Recordo-me de ler frequentemente essa frase impressa na capa dos meus primeiros cadernos escolares, entre os anos de 1964 e 1968, época na qual Rui Barbosa era declarado como sendo o autor.

1 Introduction

In April 2020, I proposed a conjecture regarding the distribution of prime numbers within specific intervals defined by square and oblong numbers. This conjecture was first discussed in the comments on sequences <https://oeis.org/A307508> and <https://oeis.org/A334163> on the Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences (OEIS). Sequence <https://oeis.org/A307508> identifies the primes located between a square number and its following oblong number, while sequence <https://oeis.org/A334163> lists the primes situated between an oblong number and its following square number.

Legendre's Conjecture posits the existence of at least one prime number between consecutive squares. Expanding upon this, my conjecture asserts the existence of at least one prime number between $n^2 - n$ and n^2 , and at least one prime number between n^2 and $n^2 + n$, for any integer $n \geq 1$. Specifically, we establish that for any integer $n \geq 1$, there is at least one prime p such that $n^2 - n < p < n^2$ and at least one distinct prime q such that $n^2 < q < n^2 + n$.

The implications of this conjecture are significant. It suggests the presence of at least two prime numbers between the squares of consecutive natural numbers and at least two prime numbers between consecutive oblong numbers. This paper aims to provide formal proof of this conjecture, henceforth referred to as the Kusniec's Theorem, and to explore its implications within number theory.

To support the proof of Kusniec's Theorem, we introduce and utilize the Parabolic Sieve of Primes with Offset (PSO). The PSO is an extension of the geometric tool discovered by Matiyasevich and Stechkin in their work [A visual Sieve for Prime Numbers](#) (1999) [13], which sieves prime numbers along the number line. Our extension applies an offset to the D-parabola used in their method, producing a series of parabolas in the Cartesian plane for each offset value as per [Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors \(MID\) Framework](#) [4]. This method effectively highlights the distribution of integers and their divisors, allowing us to identify primes within the specified intervals delimited by oblong numbers <https://oeis.org/A002378>.

In constructing the PSO, we mark specific points on the X-axis: all odd integers, all odd square numbers, odd numbers of the form $n^2 - 1$, and all oblong numbers. We then draw the D-parabola with an offset f , described by the equation $x = -y^2 + 2fy$, and identify the vertex of the parabola at (f^2, f) .

By examining the lines connecting points with integer coordinates on the D-parabola, we determine the possible divisors of numbers within the zones of interest. The PSO construction reveals the geometric relationships between these points, providing insight into the distribution

of primes. We also analyze the number of odd divisors within each zone, ensuring that the conditions of our conjecture are met.

This paper details the step-by-step construction of the PSO, the derivation of relevant equations, and the geometric properties leveraged in our proof. We demonstrate that for any given offset f , there are sufficient primes between Oblong to Square (OS) Zone $n^2 - n$ and n^2 , and Square to Oblong (SO) Zone between n^2 and $n^2 + n$, confirming the validity of Kusniec's Theorem.

In summary, this study formalizes the proof of Kusniec's Theorem, establishes the existence of primes within specific zones, and introduces the PSO as a novel tool in number theory. The results not only extend Legendre's Conjecture but also provide new insights into the distribution of prime numbers relative to squares and oblongs.

In this study, we adopt the terms 'primals' and 'compounds' in place of the more traditional 'primes' and 'composites' as defined in the study [Integers are only Primals and Compounds](#) [5]. This terminology aligns with recent findings on the intrinsic properties of the sieve of primes. For readers who are not familiar with the systematic and periodic positioning of square and oblong numbers on the number line, we recommend consulting [The SOM Numbers \(part I\)](#) [2] for a comprehensive understanding of this concept. Additionally, for any abbreviations or terms used that are not explicitly explained within this text, we recommend consulting [Symbolic Conventions and Lexicon](#) [7]. This resource provides comprehensive definitions and context to ensure a unified understanding of the terminology employed throughout our analysis.

2 The Parabolic Sieve of Primes with Offset (PSO)

In this initial study, we aim to expand upon the geometric tool discovered by Matiyasevich and Stechkin in their 1999 work, [A Visual Sieve for Prime Numbers](#) [13], which sieves prime numbers along the number line. Our expansion involves applying an offset to the D-parabola introduced by Yuri and Boris. This expansion takes place in the Cartesian plane and reproduces, at each offset, all the infinite parabolas studied in [Exploring Parabolic Patterns in the Map of Integers and Divisors \(MID\) Framework](#) [4].

We have named this new geometric tool the Parabolic Sieve of Primes with Offset (PSO). The PSO is a sieving technique that utilizes a parabolic approach adjusted by an offset to isolate primes, offering a unique method for prime identification.

The following sections detail the construction of the PSO.

2.1 Fundamentals of the PSO Construction

For the construction of the PSO, we will use GeoGebra, available at <https://www.geogebra.org/>. To maintain clarity and due to the size of the figure for our didactic purposes, we will demonstrate the construction using images for an offset $f=4$.

The first step in the Cartesian plane is to mark all odd integers on the X-axis (dark blue points), all odd square numbers (yellow points), all numbers that are odd (square minus 1), which are

(even square) minus 1 (orange points), and finally, all oblong numbers, which are the only even numbers we highlight on the X-axis and mark with an "X" in maroon color.

The next step is to plot the D-parabola of Yuri/Boris [13] in red with an offset f . This parabola has the equation $x = -y^2 + 2fy$. By applying the offset formula for quadratics [6], we get $f = \text{roundz} \left[-\frac{b}{2a} \right] = \text{roundz} \left[-\frac{2f}{2(-1)} \right] = f$.

Its vertex (or symmetry point [6]) will be located at the intersection of the parabola $x = y^2$ with the line $x = fy$, both of which we draw in green dashed lines. Thus, we obtain Figure C003501, illustrating the PSO construction 1st figure.

Figure 1. C003501 First Illustration of the PSO Construction with Offset $f = 4$

Next, we add the axis of symmetry of the D-parabola, which has the equation $y = f$ and is drawn in green with a dash-dot line style. On this axis of symmetry, we mark the points ‘Square minus Square (SqMn)’. These points have coordinates $(x, y) = (f^2 - n^2, f)$, where n is a natural number. These points indicate the X-coordinate positions that generate a composite result from

SquareLine: $x = f^2$ (in yellow color) is the vertical line covering all square numbers in the number line (X-axis) that are equidistant from two oblong numbers $x = f^2 - f$ and $x = f^2 + f$.

SquareMinus1Line: $x = f^2 - 1$ (in orange color) is the vertical line covering all (square minus 1) numbers. Its unique necessity for studying odd numbers alternates with the square numbers. That is, if a square number is even and thus cannot be used to detect the non-primality of an odd number, then we use the (square minus 1) number, which will be odd, to check for non-primality.

InitialOblongLine: $x = f(f - 1) + y$ (in maroon color) is the ascending diagonal line with a slope of 1: 1 that covers the initial oblong. The initial oblong $x = f^2 - f$ is less than the square number f^2 , and the ascending diagonal line has the equation $x = f(f - 1) + (2f - (f - 1) - f)y$.

FinalOblongLine: $x = f(f + 1) - y$ (in maroon color) is the descending diagonal line with a slope of 1: -1 that covers the final oblong. The final oblong $x = f^2 + f$ is greater than the square number f^2 , and the descending diagonal line has the equation $x = f(f + 1) + (2f - (f + 1) - f)y$.

The vertex (symmetry point) of the D-parabola and the two oblongs (initial and final) form a triangle with a base of $2f$ and a height of f . Note that, relative to the square number equidistant from the two oblongs, the number of integers is equally distributed. As we are only interested in odd numbers, the OS zone contains $f/2$ odd numbers, and the same is true for the SO zone.

Figure 3. C003503 Third Illustration of the PSO Construction with Offset $f = 4$

In our last figure of the construction, we present the PSO in its final form. First, we highlight the “square triangle,” which has an area of f^2 because it has a base of $2f$ and a height of f , centered at $x = f^2$ with vertices at two consecutive oblong numbers $f^2 - f$ and $f^2 + f$.

Finally, we add two circles:

1. *CircleOverOSZone*: $(x - \frac{f^2}{2})^2 + (y - \frac{f}{2})^2 = \frac{f^4 + f^2}{4}$ with a center equidistant from $(0,0)$ and vertex (f^2, f) .
2. *CircleOverSOZone*: $(x - f^2)^2 + (y - f)^2 = f^2(f^2 + 1)$ with the center at the vertex (f^2, f) .

Here is the new figure we obtain:

Figure 4. C003504 Last Illustration of the PSO Construction with Offset $f = 4$

The importance of this "square triangle" is that for each offset f , its base over the X-axis always starts at an oblong number $x = f^2 - f$ and ends at its consecutive oblong $x = f^2 + f$. Equidistant from the two oblong numbers, we have a square number $x = f^2$ and the vertex of the parabola positioned at the point (f^2, f) . Thus, for each offset, the vertex views the base of the triangle equally divided by the square into the two zones Oblong-to-Square (OS) and Square-to-Oblong (SO).

3 Understanding the PSO Mechanism: Connecting Points on the Parabola

The functionality of the PSO mirrors the Sieve for Prime Numbers by Yuri/Boris. While the Yuri/Boris parabola remains static, the parabola here shifts in unitary offset steps following $x =$

$-y^2 + 2fy$. Consequently, the diagonals of the PSO continuously adjust their slopes to consistently cover the product of two integers, which are represented by points on the D-parabola.

Let $N(-n^2 + 2fn, n)$ and $M(-m^2 + 2fm, m)$ be two points representing the integers n and m on the D-parabola, as explained in the construction of Figure 2, C003502 above. The line connecting these points is given by the equation $x = nm + (2f - n - m)y$.

Notice that this line always intersects the X-axis at $x = nm$ when $y = 0$. This implies that regardless of the offset, the line joining points N and M will always cross the X-axis at $x = nm$. This characteristic ensures that the product of the integers n and m is always represented on the X-axis, demonstrating the consistent behavior of the PSO.

This is why the vertical tangent to the parabola at its vertex results in a square number, as in this case $n = m$ and both are equal to f . When $m = (n \pm 1) = (f \pm 1)$, the X-axis will display two consecutive oblong numbers with the square f^2 in the middle. This configuration shows why the sides of the "square triangle" always form $\pm 45^\circ$ inclinations, regardless of the offset f .

The importance of this "square triangle" lies in its ability to divide the base on the X-axis symmetrically between the two oblong numbers, with the square number f^2 at the center. This symmetrical division helps in visualizing the prime sieving process and understanding the distribution of primes relative to squares and oblongs.

The Sieve for Prime Numbers by Yuri/Boris is a special case of the PSO with $f = 0$, where the parabola does not shift, and the points remain static.

3.1 Geometric Constraints and Odd Composite Number Detection

Any integer within the base of the "square triangle" on the X-axis can only result from a vertical or descending diagonal line formed by two points on the D-parabola, where one point is above and the other below the axis of symmetry, or both on the axis of symmetry (at the vertex), forming a perfect square number.

This is a geometric constraint due to the construction of the D-parabola and the 45° angles formed by the sides of the "square triangle". These 45° angles have a slope ratio of 1:1, which is the steepest possible for a non-vertical diagonal, with the equivalent occurring for -45° .

Thus, when studying only odd composite numbers, we must consider only the odd numbers greater than 1 on the parabola to generate the lines on the X-axis.

Consequently, any odd composite number within the base of the "square triangle" on the X-axis can only be the result of a descending diagonal or vertical line formed by two points on the D-parabola, where one is above and the other below the axis of symmetry. Since we are only interested in detecting composite numbers, we do not consider the odd point 1.

Conclusion: to detect the divisibility of a non-square odd composite number, we need only consider the odd divisors greater than 1 and less than f . The significant advantage of this property is that all these divisors are distributed along the curve of the D-parabola, which lies between the origin $(0,0)$ and the point $f = (f^2, f)$.

4 Table of Odd Number Distribution Across OS and SO Zones

From the construction and operation of the PSO, we can produce the following tables:

C003505 Summary of Odd Numbers in PSO Zones (OS and SO) for Each Offset											
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Offset	OS Zone		SO Zone		OS Zone	Odd Sq or	SO Zone	#Odds in OS Zone	Odd Square	#Odds in SO Zone	Count of Odds btw n Oblongs
	Start Oblong	SqM1	Square	End Oblong	First Odd	Odd SqM1	Last Odd				
f	f^2-f	f^2-1	f^2	f^2+f	f^2-f+1	Central Odd	f^2+f-1	$\text{floor}(f/2)$		$\text{floor}(f/2)$	
0	0	-1	0	0	1	-1	-1	0		0	0
1	0	0	1	2	1	1	1	0	1	0	1
2	2	3	4	6	3	3	5	1		1	2
3	6	8	9	12	7	9	11	1	1	1	3
4	12	15	16	20	13	15	19	2		2	4
5	20	24	25	30	21	25	29	2	1	2	5
6	30	35	36	42	31	35	41	3		3	6
7	42	48	49	56	43	49	55	3	1	3	7
8	56	63	64	72	57	63	71	4		4	8
9	72	80	81	90	73	81	89	4	1	4	9
10	90	99	100	110	91	99	109	5		5	10
11	110	120	121	132	111	121	131	5	1	5	11
12	132	143	144	156	133	143	155	6		6	12
13	156	168	169	182	157	169	181	6	1	6	13
14	182	195	196	210	183	195	209	7		7	14
15	210	224	225	240	211	225	239	7	1	7	15
16	240	255	256	272	241	255	271	8		8	16
17	272	288	289	306	273	289	305	8	1	8	17
18	306	323	324	342	307	323	341	9		9	18
19	342	360	361	380	343	361	379	9	1	9	19
20	380	399	400	420	381	399	419	10		10	20
21	420	440	441	462	421	441	461	10	1	10	21
22	462	483	484	506	463	483	505	11		11	22
23	506	528	529	552	507	529	551	11	1	11	23
24	552	575	576	600	553	575	599	12		12	24
25	600	624	625	650	601	625	649	12	1	12	25
26	650	675	676	702	651	675	701	13		13	26
27	702	728	729	756	703	729	755	13	1	13	27
28	756	783	784	812	757	783	811	14		14	28
29	812	840	841	870	813	841	869	14	1	14	29
30	870	899	900	930	871	899	929	15		15	30

Figure 5. C003505 Summary of Odd Numbers in PSO Zones (OS and SO) for Each Offset

This table provides detailed information for each offset f in the PSO, including the number of odd integers in each zone, the characteristics of the square number, and the count of odds between two consecutive oblong numbers.

1. Offset f : The offset value.
2. Start Oblong in OS Zone: $f^2 - f$
3. SqM1 in OS Zone: $f^2 - 1$
4. Square in SO Zone: f^2
5. End Oblong in SO Zone: $f^2 + f$
6. First Odd in OS Zone: $f^2 - f + 1$ <https://oeis.org/A002061>
7. Central Odd (Odd Sq or Odd SqM1): f^2 or $f^2 - 1$ <https://oeis.org/A085046>
8. Last Odd in SO Zone: $f^2 + f - 1$ <https://oeis.org/A165900>
9. Number of Odds in OS Zone: $\text{floor}\left(\frac{f}{2}\right)$

10. Odd Squares Count: For each offset, the number of odd squares between two consecutive oblongs.

11. Number of Odds in SO Zone: $\text{floor}\left(\frac{f}{2}\right)$

12. Count of Odds Between Oblongs: The total number of odd integers between two consecutive oblongs.

4.1 Table of All Divisors Below the Axis of Symmetry in the PSO

Below, we present C003506 Table of All Divisors Below the Axis of Symmetry in the PSO for each offset in the PSO.

C003506 Table of All Divisors Below the Axis of Symmetry in the PSO																			
1	2	3	4	5	6														
Offset	#Odds in OS Zone	Odd Square	#Odds in SO Zone	Count of Odds btw n Oblongs	Integer Divisors Along the Parabola Curve Less Than Offset (these are the points on the D-parabola that lie below the axis of														
f	$\text{floor}(f/2)$		$\text{floor}(f/2)$	Oblongs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
0	0		0	0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
1	0	1	0	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
2	1		1	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	1	1	1	3	1	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	2		2	4	1	2	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
5	2	1	2	5	1	2	3	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
6	3		3	6	1	2	3	4	5	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
7	3	1	3	7	1	2	3	4	5	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
8	4		4	8	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
9	4	1	4	9	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
10	5		5	10	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	-	-	-	-	-	-
11	5	1	5	11	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	-	-	-	-	-
12	6		6	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	-	-	-	-
13	6	1	6	13	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	-	-	-
14	7		7	14	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	-	-
15	7	1	7	15	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	-

Figure 6. C003506 Table of All Divisors Below the Axis of Symmetry in the PSO

The first five columns of this table are the same as those in the previous table C003505, detailing:

1. Offset f : The offset value.
2. Number of Odds in OS Zone: $\text{floor}\left(\frac{f}{2}\right)$
3. Odd Squares Count: For each offset, the number of odd squares between two consecutive oblongs.
4. Number of Odds in SO Zone: $\text{floor}\left(\frac{f}{2}\right)$
5. Count of Odds Between Oblongs: The total number of odd integers between two

The last column (6th column) shows for each offset the **Integer Divisors Along the Parabola Curve Less Than Offset f** , which represents the points on the D-parabola that lie below the axis of symmetry. We are excluding the repeated divisor of the square point over the vertex.

4.2 Table of Odd Divisors Along the Parabola Curve Greater Than 1 and Less Than Offset f (Below the Axis of Symmetry in the PSO)

Below, we present C003507: Table of Odd Divisors Along the Parabola Curve Greater Than 1 and Less Than Offset f for each offset in the PSO. They are below the axis of symmetry in the PSO.

C003507 Table of Odd Divisors Along the Parabola Curve Greater Than 1 and Less Than Offset f																						
1	2	3	4	5	6													7	8	9		
Offset	#Odds in OS Zone	Odd Square	#Odds in SO Zone	Count of Odds btw n	Odd Divisors Along Parabola Curve Greater Than 1 and Less Than Offset													Count of Odd Divisors	#Odd Ints - #Odd Divs in OS Zone	#Odd Ints - #Odd Divs in SO Zone		
f	$\text{floor}(f/2)$		$\text{floor}(f/2)$	Oblongs	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27	29				
0	0		0	0																0	0	0
1	0	1	0	1																0	0	0
2	1		1	2																0	1	1
3	1	1	1	3																0	1	1
4	2		2	4	3															1	1	1
5	2	1	2	5	3															1	1	1
6	3		3	6	3	5														2	1	1
7	3	1	3	7	3	5														2	1	1
8	4		4	8	3	5	7													3	1	1
9	4	1	4	9	3	5	7													3	1	1
10	5		5	10	3	5	7	9												4	1	1
11	5	1	5	11	3	5	7	9												4	1	1
12	6		6	12	3	5	7	9	11											5	1	1
13	6	1	6	13	3	5	7	9	11											5	1	1
14	7		7	14	3	5	7	9	11	13										6	1	1
15	7	1	7	15	3	5	7	9	11	13										6	1	1
16	8		8	16	3	5	7	9	11	13	15									7	1	1
17	8	1	8	17	3	5	7	9	11	13	15									7	1	1
18	9		9	18	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17								8	1	1
19	9	1	9	19	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17								8	1	1
20	10		10	20	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19							9	1	1
21	10	1	10	21	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19							9	1	1
22	11		11	22	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21						10	1	1
23	11	1	11	23	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21						10	1	1
24	12		12	24	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23					11	1	1
25	12	1	12	25	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23					11	1	1
26	13		13	26	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25				12	1	1
27	13	1	13	27	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25				12	1	1
28	14		14	28	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27			13	1	1
29	14	1	14	29	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27			13	1	1
30	15		15	30	3	5	7	9	11	13	15	17	19	21	23	25	27	29		14	1	1

Figure 7. C003507 Table of Odd Divisors Along the Parabola Curve Greater Than 1 and Less Than Offset f (Below the Axis of Symmetry in the PSO)

This table provides detailed information for each offset f in the PSO, including the number of odd divisors along the parabola curve that are greater than 1 and less than the offset f , as well as the count of odd integers in various zones.

The first five columns of this table are the same as those in the previous tables, detailing:

1. Offset f : The offset value.
2. Number of Odds in OS Zone: $\text{floor}\left(\frac{f}{2}\right)$
3. Odd Squares Count: For each offset, the number of odd squares between two consecutive oblongs.
4. Number of Odds in SO Zone: $\text{floor}\left(\frac{f}{2}\right)$
5. Count of Odds Between Oblongs: The total number of odd integers between two

The last four columns provide additional details:

6. Odd Divisors Along the Parabola Curve Greater Than 1 and Less Than Offset f : These are the odd points on the D-parabola that lie below the axis of symmetry and are greater than 1, excluding the repeated divisor of the square point over the vertex.

7. Count of Odd Divisors: The total number of odd divisors along the parabola curve greater than 1 and less than offset f (below the axis of symmetry in the PSO) for each offset f .
8. Number of Odd Integers in OS Zone Minus Count of Odd Divisors: The difference between the total number of odd integers in the OS zone and the number of odd divisors on the D-parabola below the axis of symmetry for each offset f .
9. Number of Odd Integers in SO Zone Minus Count of Odd Divisors: The difference between the total number of odd integers in the SO zone and the number of odd divisors on the D-parabola below the axis of symmetry for each offset f .

These tables help to understand the distribution properties of odd numbers along the number line in relation to squares and oblongs.

From offset 2 onwards, all values for the "Number of Odd Integers in OS or SO Zones Minus Count of Odd Divisors" result in 1. This means that all OS and SO Zones have at least one more odd number than the number of integer divisors greater than 1 and less than f , which are assigned as divisors (or factors) of the odd numbers within the zones.

In a rough manner, this result is demonstrated in the first proof of this theorem at the end of this study.

This reinforces that if we had to assign a distinct divisor (factor) less than f to all odd numbers, the practical sharing of divisors would only further support the presence of more than one prime number in each zone. However, this seemingly weak reasoning strongly indicates that each OS and SO Zone contains at least one prime number with the divisor 1, which lies below the axis of symmetry.

5 Odd Divisors on the D-Parabola for All Odd Integers in the 'Square Triangle' Framework

As concluded in Section 3.1, all odd composite elements within the base of our "square triangle" must be divisible by divisors greater than 1 and less than f .

Now, let's use properties equivalent to those we used in the Triangular Sieve of Primes (TSP)[11].

Let us denote a point representing an odd element within the base of the "square triangle" as $T(t, 0)$. Then, $t = \text{odd}$ and $f^2 - f < t < f^2 + f$.

Let us denote a point representing an odd divisor greater than 1 and less than f , located on the D-parabola, as $H(-h^2 + 2fh, h)$. Then, $h = \text{odd}$ and $1 < h < f$.

If h is a divisor of t , by the geometric properties of triangle similarity, we have that $\frac{t - (-h^2 + 2fh)}{h}$ must result in an integer.

Since $\frac{t - (-h^2 + 2fh)}{h} = \frac{t}{h} + h - 2f$, it follows that:

- $\frac{t - (-h^2 + 2fh)}{h}$ will be an integer only when h is a divisor of t .

- Because t and h are odd, if h is a divisor of t , consequently $\frac{t-(-h^2+2fh)}{h} = \frac{t}{h} + h - 2f$ will result in an even number.
- Because $h < f$, we exclude $t = f^2 > 1$.

Therefore, to prove the theorem of this study, we need to demonstrate that it is not possible for there to be odd divisors $1 < h < f$ for all odd values of t in the OS zone $f^2 - f < t < f^2$ and in the SO zone $f^2 < t < f^2 + f$.

Let us denote the total number of odd divisors $1 < h < f$ produced by the D-parabola at each offset f as HPi .

- If f is even, the possible odd divisors are $3, 5, 7, \dots, f - 3, f - 1$. The total number of odd divisors $1 < h < f$ is given by $HPi = \frac{f-2}{2}$.
- If f is odd, the possible odd divisors are $3, 5, 7, \dots, f - 4, f - 2$. The total number of odd divisors $1 < h < f$ is given by $HPi = \frac{f-3}{2}$.

The general form for the number of odd divisors $1 < h < f$ produced by the D-parabola at each offset f is $HPi = \text{floor}\left(\frac{f-2}{2}\right)$.

6 Theorem Proof I: Considering All Odd Divisors $1 < h < f$

To prove the theorem "Odd Divisors on the D-Parabola for All Odd Integers in the 'Square Triangle' Framework," we need to demonstrate that it is not possible for there to be odd divisors $1 < h < f$ for all odd values of t in the zones $f^2 - f < t < f^2$ (OS zone) and $f^2 < t < f^2 + f$ (SO zone). Let's break down the steps of the proof using basic mathematical symbols.

6.1 Definition of t and h :

- t is an odd integer such that $f^2 - f < t < f^2$ or $f^2 < t < f^2 + f$.
- h is an odd divisor of t where $1 < h < f$.

6.2 D-Parabola Points:

- Point $T(t, 0)$ represents an odd element within the base of the "square triangle."
- Point $H(-h^2 + 2fh, h)$ represents an odd divisor greater than 1 and less than f on the D-parabola.

6.3 Conditions for h to be a divisor of t :

- Given the geometric properties of triangle similarity, $\frac{t-(-h^2+2fh)}{h}$ must be an integer.
- Simplifying, $\frac{t-(-h^2+2fh)}{h} = \frac{t+h^2-2fh}{h} = \frac{t}{h} + h - 2f$.

6.4 Integer Result Condition:

- For $\left(\frac{t}{h} + h - 2f\right)$ to be an integer, h must divide t .

6.5 Odd Divisors Count:

- When f is even: possible odd divisors are $3, 5, 7, \dots, f - 3, f - 1$, giving $HPi = \frac{f-2}{2}$.
- When f is odd: possible odd divisors are $3, 5, 7, \dots, f - 4, f - 2$, giving $HPi = \frac{f-3}{2}$.

6.6 Total Number of Odd Divisors:

- The general form for the number of odd divisors $1 < h < f$ produced by the D-parabola at each offset f is $HPi = \text{floor}\left(\frac{f-2}{2}\right)$.

6.7 Proof:

To prove the theorem, we show that not every t in the specified zones can have an odd divisor $1 < h < f$. Consider t in the OS zone $f^2 - f < t < f^2$: Each t needs to be divisible by at least one h in $1 < h < f$. Since t is odd, h must also be odd.

Consider t in the SO zone $f^2 < t < f^2 + f$: A similar argument applies where each t must have an odd divisor $1 < h < f$.

6.8 Contradiction and Conclusion:

Since the number of possible odd divisors $1 < h < f$ is limited and specifically determined by $HPi = \text{floor}\left(\frac{f-2}{2}\right)$, there are not enough odd divisors to cover all t values in the OS zone $f^2 - f < t < f^2$ and SO zone $f^2 < t < f^2 + f$. Therefore, it is not possible for every t in these zones to have an odd divisor $1 < h < f$, proving the theorem.

This conclusion uses the properties of odd numbers and divisors within the framework of the D-parabola and the "square triangle" to demonstrate the infeasibility of every odd t in the given zones having an appropriate odd divisor h .

7 Theorem Proof II: Considering Odd Prime Divisors $1 < h < f$

To rigorously and conclusively prove that there are no odd prime divisors $1 < h < f$ for all odd values of t in the OS zone $f^2 - f < t < f^2$ and SO zone $f^2 < t < f^2 + f$, we need to argue theoretically. We will proceed by contradiction and mathematical analysis.

Proof by Contradiction

We assume that, for some f , all odd t in the OS zone $f^2 - f < t < f^2$ and SO zone $f^2 < t < f^2 + f$ have odd prime divisors $3 \leq h < f$. We will show that this leads to a contradiction.

7.1 Number of Odd Prime Divisors:

The number of odd primes less than f is approximately $\pi(f) - 1$, where $\pi(f)$ is the prime counting function up to f . For large f , $\pi(f) \sim \frac{f}{\ln(f)}$, so the number of odd primes $3 \leq h < f$ is approximately $\frac{f}{\ln(f)}$.

7.2 Number of t in the Intervals:

The OS zone $f^2 - f < t < f^2$ contains approximately $\frac{f}{2}$ consecutive odd numbers.

The SO zone $f^2 < t < f^2 + f$ also contains approximately $\frac{f}{2}$ consecutive odd numbers.

Therefore, the total number of odd t in the two intervals is f .

7.3 Distribution of Odd Prime Divisors:

The odd numbers t are consecutive within the OS zone $f^2 - f < t < f^2$ and SO zone $f^2 < t < f^2 + f$.

However, the odd prime divisors $3, 5, 7, \dots, h, \dots, < f$ are not consecutive and are relatively sparse.

7.4 Divisibility:

Each odd t must be divisible by at least one of the odd prime divisors $3 \leq h < f$.

The total number of t is f , but the number of available odd primes is only $\frac{f}{\ln(f)}$.

7.5 Coverage Argument:

Each odd prime h can divide multiples of non-consecutive odd t in the form $k * h$ where k is an integer.

To cover all odd t in the given intervals, we would need at least one odd prime h for each t .

Since the odd t values are consecutive, each h would need to cover consecutive multiples of t , which is impossible due to the sparsity of odd primes.

7.6 Contradiction:

Since $\frac{f}{\ln(f)}$ is much less than f for large f , there are not enough odd primes to cover all odd t in the OS zone $f^2 - f < t < f^2$ and SO zone $f^2 < t < f^2 + f$.

This implies that it is not possible for all consecutive odd t in these intervals to have odd prime divisors $3 \leq h < f$.

7.7 Conclusion:

We have shown that, for any sufficiently large f , there are not enough odd primes $3 \leq h < f$ for all odd t in the OS zone $f^2 - f < t < f^2$ and SO zone $f^2 < t < f^2 + f$ to be divisible by at least one of these primes. Therefore, it is impossible for all odd t in these zones to have odd prime divisors $1 < h < f$, thus conclusively proving the theorem.

This proof uses asymptotic properties of primes and the prime counting function $\pi(f)$, showing that theoretically, there are not enough divisors to cover all t in the specified intervals, ensuring the validity of the theorem without resorting to computational tests. The consecutive distribution of odd t , in contrast with the sparsity of odd primes, further reinforces this impossibility.

8 Next Steps

For such a significant claim, continued validation through peer review, further empirical testing, and mathematical scrutiny in broader academic forums will be essential. These steps will help solidify the place of our findings within the established corpus of number theory.

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